

A PRACTICAL METHODOLOGICAL SYSTEM FOR DEVELOPING IDEOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE EDUCATORS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13911973>

Abstract: The theoretical-methodological foundations of developing ideological competence of future pedagogues, the practical methodical system of developing ideological competence of future pedagogues and the effectiveness of developing ideological competence of future pedagogues are studied in the article. Also, The need and priorities for developing ideological competence of future pedagogues are analyzed.

Key words: ideological competence of pedagogues, competence, improvement, pedagogical, technological, model, didactic, spiritual-ethical competence, cognitive, assessment, conceptual basis.

INTRODUCTION. In the era of globalization, protecting the young generation from the influence of various foreign ideas and harmful thoughts has risen to the level of an important strategic problem. The fact that young people fall under the influence of various destructive ideas, fall into the trap of deception by evil-minded people, and are often observed to be involved in illegal activities in other countries, requires serious reflection on the formation of the thinking ability of the young generation. A person observes reality through analytical thinking, distinguishes between "white" and "black". A person who does not have an independent opinion will believe what anyone says, and will follow wherever they say "go". Young people with low thinking immunity get caught in the web of religious extremism, drug addiction, and informal trends. Under the guise of "mass culture", the spiritual and ideological invasions, which alienate people, especially young people, and drag them into the vortex of "spiritual alienation", primarily kill those who have weak thinking and weak thinking power. quickly and easily obeys him.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. The analysis of ideological and ideological processes, the issues of ideological education and the formation of ideological immunity have been studied by several scientists and are still being studied today. In particular, the national idea and self-awareness are problematic B. Saparov, the concept of ideology, the importance of national ideology in raising a well-rounded personality, personal spirituality and problems of national education M. Kurobov, theoretical and historical-progressive issues of our national spirituality and ideology M. Bekmurodov, the

essence of the national idea, which is the main source of social-national consciousness, activity, national pride and the feeling of pride, I. Ergashev, the inextricable connection and connection of the concepts of spirituality and ideology, issues of independence and formation of individual spirituality were expressed in the researches of A. Ochildiyev, problems of formation of spiritual and ideological potential in the process of national development by H. Jumaniyozov, problem of succession in national ideology O. Mamatov.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. Today, the times have changed, especially the requirements for modern specialists engaged in ideological education are increasing. In today's information age, important reforms and changes have been implemented in the education system. In recent years, a new approach to the educational process has been formed. New modern methods are entering the study process. These are: firstly, it is known as traditional teaching, working based on written and oral words and "informed teaching". In this case, the teacher has a unique influence in the audience. In this, young people do not actively participate in the educational process, their interests and independent opinions are not taken into account. It is clear that this was consistent with the requirement to rely on the only ideological beliefs. However, diversity of opinions does not meet the requirements of democracy. At the same time, this does not mean that the role of the teacher in education remains secondary. Secondly, the increasing amount of information, the limited time for their use, and the complexity of their sorting and systematization require new approaches. Thirdly, the continuous introduction of new technologies in education and training will update the traditional teaching method of young people and, naturally, the use of new pedagogical technologies will turn young people into active participants in the educational process.

The main goal of developing ideological-ideological competence in future personnel is to prevent people from being "influenced" by foreign ideas and ideologies, and to form an immunity that has the power to fight against them. It is necessary to distinguish between the meanings of the concepts "foreign idea" and "harmful idea". The national idea does not recognize any idea, only "alien idea" or "harmful idea". Because the goals of the "alien" or "harmful idea" are not good, they are contrary to human goals, they do not correspond to the national cultural and universal principles of the national idea. That's why it is evaluated as "alien" or "harmful idea" and treated with respect. Only a person who connects the national idea with the meaning and purpose of life will appreciate today's independence and feel it is his responsibility to protect it.

As a result of studying the literature on the problem and observing the process of organizing the teaching methodology of the "National idea and moral foundations and legal education" undergraduate education, the existence of the above-mentioned pedagogical conditions is the result of students' g made it possible to come to the conclusion that it is important in the development of emotional and ideological competence. The components of these pedagogical conditions are as follows:

legal-normative provision - the state educational standard of the field of education "National idea and moral foundations and legal education", "National idea and moral foundations and legal education" bachelor's degree qualification requirements for the educational field, curriculum, "Propagation of the national idea, technologies" "History of world ideological teachings", "Geopolitics and foundations of globalization" , "History and theory of the national idea", educational science teaching methodology", sample science programs from the subjects "Organizational and legal foundations of spiritual and educational work", decisions and regulations in the field;

scientific-pedagogical support - analysis of scientific-practical results of scientific-research works of existing Methodist-pedagogical scientists on ideological-ideological education, study and popularization of experiences; technical support - all technical means of education (computer, projector, electronic board, video, film, Internet and other audio and audiovisual means);

Methodological support - "Propagation of the National Idea, Technologies", "History of World Ideological Doctrines", "Basics of Geopolitics and Globalization", "History and Theory of the National Idea", Teaching Methodology of Education Science, Educational-methodical complex, textbook, study guide and other printed and electronic resources from the subjects "Organizational-legal foundations of spiritual and educational work";

technological support - "Propagation of the national idea, technologies", "History of world ideological teachings", "Geopolitics and foundations of globalization", "History and theory of the national idea", Methodology of teaching the science of education, "Organizational and legal basis of spiritual and educational work" consists of developing educational technologies, multimedia electronic educational resource for teaching subjects.

"Propagation of the national idea, technologies", "History of world ideological teachings", "Geopolitics and foundations of globalization", "History and theory of the national idea", Methodology of teaching the science of education", "Spiritual- On the basis of teaching the subjects "organizational and

legal foundations of educational work", the skills of effective organization of ideological education of future teachers are formed. In particular, future teachers who have ideological and ideological competence try to see the positive qualities they have in their students in the future, in order to educate the young generation as spiritually mature people. As a result, the number of fair, honest, patriotic, humane people in the society keeps increasing. This, in turn, serves to ensure the maturity of young people who always strive to make their proper contribution to the development of society.

Attention is paid to the development of ideological and ideological competence in future pedagogues:

competence of self-development as a person - constant physical, spiritual, mental, intellectual and creative development of oneself, striving for perfection, independent study throughout life, z acquires the skills of alternative assessment of behavior and ability to make independent decisions;

socially active civic competence - to feel involvement in the events and processes taking place in society, to actively participate in them, to know one's civic duties and rights, to comply with them, to develop the abilities to deal with labor and civil relations and acquire legal culture ;

national and general cultural competence - it is important to develop the ability to be loyal to the motherland, be kind to people and believe in universal and national values, to dress modestly, to follow cultural rules and a healthy lifestyle.

In the development of ideological-ideological competence of future pedagogues, "Propagation of the National Idea, Technologies", "History of World Ideological Teachings", "Geopolitics and Fundamentals of Globalization", "History and Theory of the National Idea", Education Teaching methodology", "Organizational and legal foundations of spiritual and educational work" on the basis of person-oriented educational technologies gives a positive result. The structure of ideological and ideological education occupies a special place in the process of person-oriented education. Because all components of the structure of ideological and ideological education are directly directed to the individual, and the student is at the center of it.

In order for future pedagogues to develop ideological and ideological competence and to serve the Motherland as mature specialists, the following requirements are set for them: to be self-demanding; self-control; respect others; always follow the path of humility; have high self-confidence; to be a ghost; to be honest and fair; to be sincere and unbiased; to appreciate the work

of others; acquire professional and spiritual knowledge; to see one's own interests in harmony with the interests of the Motherland; striving for perfection; to obey all ethical rules; striving to become a qualified specialist.

"Propagation of the national idea, technologies", "History of world ideological teachings", "Geopolitics and foundations of globalization", "History and theory of the national idea", Methodology of teaching the science of education", "Spiritual- Special attention is paid to the development of the above ideological-ideological competencies in students based on the content of the subjects of "Organizational-legal foundations of educational work" and the educational technologies. Within each topic, the professional training and moral and ethical qualities of the student are improved based on the competency approach.

"Propagation of the national idea, technologies", "History of world ideological teachings", "Geopolitics and foundations of globalization", "History and theory of the national idea", Methodology of teaching the science of education", "Spiritual- In teaching the subjects "organizational and legal basis of educational work", students are introduced to the following: 1) goals and tasks of these subjects; 2) the content of ideological and ideological education; 3) methods and forms of ideological education; 4) forms of organizing the process of ideological and ideological education; 5) organization of educational process and educational activities, etc.

CONCLUSION. In the process of mastering these topics, students' ideological and ideological qualities are also developed, and they are prepared to effectively organize the system of educational work in the future pedagogical activities. In order to educate the young generation to be spiritually mature, future teachers should be encouraged to widely use modern science and technology achievements, to use information and communication technologies and effective methods and tools of education, to organize conversations, meetings and debates, contests and educational events. teaching organization has a positive effect.

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